

Role of Women In Agriculture and Animal Husbandry Development– A Geographical Analysis of Block Joya, District Amroha

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Abstract

Mostly population lives in rural areas in India. Almost 70% rural population is engaged in agriculture and animal husbandry. Women play an important role in animal husbandry. They clean the cattle shed, care of the cattle, management of the fodder, milking, watering and feeding etc. regularly. They process the dairy products and marketing its. Not only women participate in animal husbandry but also participate in agriculture production. Dairy industry is developing in rural areas due to the participation of the women in animal husbandry. They contribute in increasing the income of the family. Animal husbandry plays an important role in generating the employment in rural areas. Agriculture sector one of the most important source of employment in rural areas which provide the raw materials to run the industries. Mixed agriculture is developed in rural areas and providing the employment opportunities in rural areas. Not only, farmers produce the crops but also work animal husbandry. Due to low level of literacy of the rural women they are engaged in primary sector like that agriculture activities and animal husbandry.

Keywords

Animal Husbandry, Participation, Empowerment, Primary Activities, Cattle Shed.

Introduction

India is a developing country. Its economy is based on agriculture. Almost 70% population of rural areas is engaged in agriculture and its sub activities. It is a main source of employment in rural areas. Animal husbandry is secondary source of employment in rural areas. Its provide employment mostly to the unskilled workers. Due to low literacy in rural areas and lack of the employment sources mostly population is engaged in agriculture sector. So the engagement of the women is higher in animal husbandry than the male participation. Women participation seems in harvesting, the crops and management the fodder of the cattle. They care the cattle and clean the cattle shed regularly. They participate in agriculture activities too. They increase the income of household by working in agriculture as a worker. Women work is very important in agriculture and animal husbandry. So women are known multitasking workers in rural areas. Not only women are management the household works but also participate in agriculture and animal husbandry works.

According to the annual report of P.L.F.S. 2022–23 agriculture had the highest estimated percentage distribution of female workers 64.3%. In rural areas the participation of women in agriculture was 76.2% in and 11.7% in urban areas in 2022–23 in India. In the progress of the rural economy women have important place because they play multiple roles a farmers, wages, earners and entrepreneurs. They also care for the well being of their family members and are responsible for providing the food and care to the children and the elderly. Women comprise 33% of the agriculture labour force and 48% of the self employed farmers in India. Due to growing urban migration by men the agriculture sector is being managed by women. So women contribute to agriculture through multiple role as cultivations, entrepreneurs and laborers.

Objective of study

To complete the present study the researcher has selected the following objectives–

1. To analyse the participation of the rural women in agriculture and animal husbandry in the study area.
2. To analyse the socio-economic status of the rural women which are engaged in primary sector in the study area.
3. To analyse the basic problems of the rural women which are engaged in agriculture activities and animal husbandry.

**Review of
Literature**

To complete the present study the researcher studied various research works related to the women participation in agriculture and animal husbandry. Some selected literature related to the research problem are present here–

Lal and Khurana (2011) presented a research paper entitled “Gender issues: The role of women in agriculture sector.” They analysed that rural women are the major contributors in agriculture and its allied fields. Women's labour power is considered inferior because of employers predetermined notion of women's primary role as homemakers. As a result of discrimination against female labour women are concentrated in the secondary sector of labour market.

Chauhan (2011) conducted a study on tribal farm women in agricultural and animal husbandry in Gujarat. He analysed that farm women made their own decisions for home management, including choosing and preparing meals (70.83%) and decorating the house (79.17%). The majority of farm management decisions were made by the wives husbands and women entirely controlled animal husbandry.

Ghosh and Ghosh (2014) analysed that women constituted 38% of the agriculture labour force in developing countries. It is also estimated that 45.3% of the agricultural labour force consists of women. But a large number of women have remained as invisible workers. They analysed the women empowerment and the management work of agriculture and animal husbandry.

Bhanotra, Wankhande, Khandey and Kumar (2015) presented a research paper entitled “Role of rural women in decision making process regarding livestock management.” They analysed that livestock management has always been considered to the sole responsibility of women. Rural women play a crucial role in rural economic growth. They embark on various activities of livestock management like watering and feeding of animals, cleaning activities and milking etc. They found that the women participation is higher in feeding, cleaning and caring the cattle's baby than the male participation in animal husbandry.

Jayasheela (2015) presented a research paper entitled “The role of women in Indian agriculture sector.” She discussed the contribution of women in agriculture and analysed her work ranges from crop production, live stock production, to cottage industry. Women spent long hours fetching water, doing laundry, making food and carrying out agricultural duties. Women occupational choices are very limited in rural areas due to social and cultural constraints, gender bias in the labour markets and lack of supportive facilities such as child care, transport and accommodation in the formal sector of the labour market.

Sharma (2018) presented a research paper related to the women participation in milk production and dairy farming. They analysed that in zone 03 of Rajasthan women have emerged as key stakeholders in milk production and the utilization of dairy farming. Women's participation not only enhances milk production and quality but also leads to economic growth, empowerment and social development in the region.

Govindasamy and Das (2021) analysed the participation of women in agriculture sector in the context of India. They analysed that women's participation rate in the agricultural sectors is about 47% in tea plantations, 46.84% in cotton cultivation, 45.43% growing oil seeds and 39.13% in vegetables production.

Sarkar (2022) presented a research paper entitled “Women participation in the agriculture sector in Andman and Nicobar Islands.” They analysed that agriculture is the backbone of rural economy. It is a big source of employment in rural areas. They analysed that agriculture is an engine of development and poverty alleviation in developing countries like India and here it is the main occupation of the poor.

Pandey and Rai (2023) presented a research paper entitled “Involvement of rural women in animal husbandry decision-making.” They analysed that the involvement of rural women in decision making process related to animal husbandry is crucial for sustainable agriculture practices and rural development. The results also reveal variations in participation levels across different animal husbandry practice.

Kumari and Roy (2023) presented a research paper entitled “Role of women in agriculture and its allied fields in India.” They found that women have contributed significantly to the growth of the agricultural sector and other associated industries. Land preparation, sowing, nursery management, transplanting, weeding, irrigation, fertilizers application, plant protection, harvesting, storing and other agricultural duties are all performed by women.

Bidhan, Tyagi and Chander (2024) analysed that women play a crucial position in milk production, participating in both livestock management and agricultural production. They found that animal husbandry is the second most important economic activity in rural areas after agriculture, generating income and employment for rural households.

Hypothesis

The following hypothesis has been selected to complete the present study-

1. Women participation is higher in primary sector than the men participation in the study area.
2. Socio-economic status of the rural women is very poor which are engaged in primary sector in the study area.
3. Low wages and gender discrimination are the main problems of the women agriculture labour in the study area.

Methodology

Both types of data has been used to complete the present study. Primary data has been collected by personal interview method by using the questionnaire and schedule related to the research problems. Field survey method has been used to collect the primary data related to the engage of the women in agriculture and animal husbandry activities. Secondary data has been collected from the district statistical magazines of Amroha district, statistical magazines of Joya block, journals, officials reports related to the women employment and different websites. Statistical methods has been used to analyse the data to finding the result. Tabulation and graphical methods have been used to present the level of the research problems.

Sampling

To complete the present study the researcher has collected 200 sample from the study area by using the randomly sampling methods. The following sample design has been used to collect the primary data-

Sample Design

S.No.	Variables	No. of Respondents
1.	Farmers	50
2.	Labour in agriculture activities	50
3.	Animal Husbandry	50
4.	Unorganized sector labour	50
Total		200

Analysis

Statement of The Research Problem

The development of rural economy is depends on the primary sector development. Due to high population pressure on the agriculture and use of technology in agriculture the problems of employment and migration are increasing in rural areas. The burden of the household works, animals husbandry works and agricultural activities works has fallen on the shoulders of women in rural areas. Due to low literacy level of the women in rural areas mostly women are engaged in agriculture related works. So their monthly average income is very poor in the rural areas. The problem of gender discrimination is present in rural area and they are facing it. They face significant barriers to formal jobs earn less than men for similar work and are concentrated in low paying unprotected informal sectors.

Study Area

To complete the present study the researcher has selected block Joya. It is situated in district Amroha. It has covered 415.60 km² geographical area. It is created the political boundary with the Moradabad and Sambhal district. It is bounded by Amroha block in the north and bounded by Moradabad district in the east and bounded by district Sambhal in the south and bounded by the block Hasanpur in the south west. Gajraula block is situated in the west part of this block. National highway 24 runs through Joya and connecting it to Delhi and Moradabad. U.P. state highway 77 also passages through Joya block knows as Nahataur-Noorpur-Amroha-Joya road. It is started from Joya block headquarter. According to the census of 2011 total population 2.87 lakh lives in Joya block within 193 villages.

Occupational Structure of The Women In The Study Area

in the present study the researcher has analysed the occupational structure of the study area block Joya. Mostly population is engaged in the primary sector of the study area due to the problem of employment opportunities. On the basis of the 200 samples the researcher has analysed the occupational structure of the study area. Which is given below in the table-

Table-1
Occupational Structure of the Selected Women in the Study Area, Block Joya (October-2025)

Sr.No.	Occupational Structure	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	Primary Sector	155	77.50
2.	Secondary Sector	32	16.00
3.	Territory Sector	13	6.50
Total		200	100

Source: Computed by the author on the basis of the sample survey, October-2025

On the basis of the sample survey the researcher analysed the women occupational structure of the study area block Joya. In the present study the research found that 77.50% women are engaged in primary sector, 16% women engaged in secondary sector and 6.50% women are engaged in territory sector in the study area. So the agriculture is the main occupation of the rural women. They work as a farmer and labour in agriculture.

Participation of Women In Agriculture Production

Agriculture sector is one of the most important source of the employment in rural area. Almost 70% population is engaged in agriculture sector in rural area. Women participation in agriculture sector is increasing here due to migration the male workers in urban areas. Different types of works are performed by the women in agriculture like that harvesting, sowing the crops, watering the crops, weeding collecting the fodder for cattle etc. So women role is very crucial in agricultural production. On the basis of the sample survey the researcher collected the data related to the women participation in agriculture. Which is given below in the table-

Table-2
Participation of Women in Agriculture Production in the Study Area Block Joya (October-2025)

S.No.	Agriculture Activities	No. of Sample	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Harvesting the crops	200	131	65.50
2.	Sowing the crops	200	116	58.00
3.	Weeding the crops	200	105	52.50
4.	Watering the crops	200	64	32.00
Mean \bar{x}		200	104	52.00

Source: Computed by the author on the basis of the sample survey, October-2025

On the basis of the 200 sample the researcher analysed that 52% women are engaged in agricultural activities. There are 65.50% women are engaged in harvesting the crops, 58% women engaged in sowing the crops activities and 52.50% women are engaged in weeding the crops activities in the study area. There are 32% women are engaged in watering the crops. So we found that women participation is higher in harvesting the crops in the study area.

Women Participation In Animal Husbandry

Animal husbandry is one of the most important source of income with the agriculture production of the farmers in rural areas. Mostly farmers prefer the practice of the mixed farming to solve the problem of income, milk, manure, fuel and livestock etc. Male and female both work of the animal husbandry but the participation of women is higher than the male participation in animal husbandry. Women are the backbone of the animal husbandry in rural areas. Women's contribution is better in management of the fodder, milking and processing, manure management, cleaning the cattle shed, care of the cattle and their child etc. Women participation in animal husbandry helps to increase the income of households and helps in reduce the poverty in rural areas. The participation of women in animal husbandry is given below in the table–

Table-3
Participation of Women in Animal Husbandry in the Study Area Block Joya (October-2025)

Sr.No.	Activities	No. of Sample	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Feeding	200	135	67.50
2.	Watering	200	142	71.00
3.	Cleaning	200	167	83.50
4.	Milking and processing	200	162	81.00
5.	Caring of diseased	200	170	85.00
6.	Grazing	200	63	31.50
7.	Marketing	200	52	26.00
8.	Collecting the fodder	200	146	73.00
Mean \bar{x}		200	130	65.00

Source: Computed by the author on the basis of the sample survey, October-2025

On the basis of the sample survey the researcher found that 65% women are engaged in animal husbandry in the study area. On the basis of the 200 sample related to the participation of women in animal husbandry the researcher has found that 67.50% women are engaged in feeding works of animal husbandry, 71.0% in watering, 83.50% in cleaning the cattle shed, 81% in milking and processing works, 85% are engaged in caring the animals during the illness, 31.50% in grazing the cattle, 26% in marketing the cattle and 73% women are engaged in collecting the fodder from the field to fulfill the requirement of the feeding. On the basis of the analysed the data the researcher found that the role of women is very important in animal husbandry.

Socio-Economic Status of The Selected Women

To find out the result related to the socio-economic status of the rural women the researcher analysed the literacy level and educational status of the women and about the calculation of the economic status the researcher analysed the per month income of the selected women. Socio-economic status of the selected women is given below in the table–

Table-4
Social Status of the Selected Women of the Study Area, Block Joya (October-2025)

S.No.	Educational Status	Total No. of Sample	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	Literate	200	95	47.50
2.	Illiterate	200	105	52.50
3.	Basic education	200	32	16.00
4.	Senior basic education	200	27	13.50
5.	High school	200	21	10.50
6.	Intermediate	200	12	6.00
7.	Graduate	200	03	1.50

Source: Computed by the author on the basis of the sample survey, October-2025

According to the above table the researcher analysed that the literacy rate of women is 47.50% of the selected sample and 52.50% women are illiterate in the study area. The researcher has also analysed the women educational status, which is as– there are 16% women have the basic education till 5th class and 13.50% women have senior basic education till 8th class, 10.50% women have passed high school and 6.00% women have passed intermediate class here. We found that 1.50% women have the graduation degree which is engaged in agriculture activities in the study area.

Economic Status of The Selected Women

On the basis of the per month average income of the women the researcher has analysed the economic status of the selected women. These women are engaged in agricultural activities, animal husbandry and other works in the study area. The economic status of the selected women is given below in the table–

Table–5
Economic Status of the Selected Women of the Study Area
Block Joya (October–2025)

Income Group (in Rs.)	No. of Respondents	Percentage
0 – 1000	41	20.50
1001 – 2000	28	14.00
2001 – 3000	47	23.50
3001 – 4000	55	27.50
4001 – 5000	17	8.50
> 5000	12	6.00
Total	200	100

Source: Computed by the author on the basis of the sample survey, October–2025

According to the above table the researcher has found that 20.50% women's per month income is below 1000 Rs. and 14.00% women's per month income is between 1001–2000 Rs. There are 23.50% women's per month income is between 2001–3000 Rs. and 27.50% women's per month income is between 3001–4000 Rs. and 8.50% women have income between 4001–5000 Rs. per month. There are 6% women's income is more than 5000 Rs. per month in the study area. According to the above data we can say that 58% women's per month income is below 3000 Rs. in the study area. So the economic level of the agriculture labour is poor in the study area.

Gender Discrimination in Wages

Gender wages discrimination is significant problem in rural areas with female workers. Women are concentrated in lower and jobs, especially in agriculture with less access to better paying non-farm work leading to lower overall earnings. Land lord and contractors discriminate with the female workers in agriculture activities and non-farm. Due to low literacy, poverty, unemployment and the poor transportation facilities etc. are also responsible to discrimination with the women in wages in rural areas. On the basis of the sample survey the researcher analysed the gender discrimination in wages in the study area. The discrimination in wages between male and female is presented in the table–

Table–6
Gender Discrimination in Wages in Agricultural Activities in the Study Area,
Block Joya (October–2025)

S.No.	Particulars	Average Per Month Wages (in Rs.)		Variation
		Male	Female	
1.	Agriculture Labour	3600	3000	600
2.	Animal husbandry labour	3500	3000	500
3.	Unorganized manufacturing sector	6700	4200	1500

Source: Computed by the author on the basis of the sample survey, October–2025.

According to the above table the variation in the wages of male and female workers has found in the study area. Male agriculture labour is getting 3600 Rs. per month in agriculture but in the same work women is getting 3000 Rs. per month here. The researcher found 600 Rs. per month variation in wages of male and female in same work in agriculture sector. In animal husbandry activities male labour is getting 3500 Rs. per month and female labour is getting 3000 Rs. per month. There is 500 Rs. variation between male and female wages in same work in animal husbandry. Unorganised sector is developing in rural areas and providing the employment to the rural population. The average wages of male worker has found 6700 Rs. per month in unorganized sector but the wages of female workers has found 4200 Rs. per month in same work. The variation has

found 1500 Rs. per month between male and female works in same jobs. So we can say that the gender discrimination is present in wages in rural areas.

Unemployment

Due to main sources of employment the agriculture sector is unable to provide to employment for every hand in rural areas. So the problems are increasing like that poverty, poor wages, gender discrimination in wages, unemployment and disguised unemployment etc. in rural areas. Mostly families are unable to get the whole year employment to available the seasonal employment in agriculture and agro-based industries. On the basis of the sample survey the researcher analysed the rate of unemployment of the study area, which is given below in the table–

Table-7
Rate of Unemployment of the Women in the Study Area, Block Joya (October-2025)

No. of Working Days	No. of Respondents	Percentage
0 – 60	28	14.00
60 – 120	25	12.50
120 – 180	97	48.50
180 – 240	23	11.50
240 – 300	15	7.50
> 300	12	6.00
Total	200	100

Source: Computed by the author on the basis of the sample survey, October-2025.

According to the above table there are 14% women got employment less than 60 days in the study area in the year 2024–2025 and 12.50% women got employment 60–120 days. There are 48.50% women got employment 120–180 days in the study area. There are 11.50% women got employment 180–240 days in a financial year in block Joya in agriculture and its activities. There are 7.50% women got employment 240–300 days and 6.00% women got employment more than 300 days in a financial year. So we can say that the agriculture sector is unable to provide the employment in whole year. We found that 13.50% women got employment in agriculture more than 240 days in a year in the study area.

High Population Growth

High population growth is responsible to poverty and unemployment because the pressure of the population is increasing on the agriculture sector. So the problem of unemployment is increasing here. Due to big size of family the rate of dependency on working population is increasing here. The growth of population of the study area is given below in the table–

Table-8
Trends of Population Growth in the Study Area Block Joya
(1991-2011)

Year	Population	Population Growth	Decadal Growth in %
1991	214600	-	-
2001	270297	55697	29.95
2011	287947	17650	6.53

Source: District Statistical Magazine, District Amroha, Year 2001, 2011 and 2024.

On the basis of the above table the decadal growth of population was 29.95% in 1991-2001 in block Joya and it was 6.53% in 2001-2011 here. During in this period 1991-2001 the growth of population was found very high and it is increasing day by day. So the pressure on agriculture is increasing here.

Findings

In the present study the researcher found that the participation of women in agriculture production and animal husbandry is very important in process the rural economy. The researcher found that 77.50% women are engaged in agricultural and animal husbandry activities in the study area. We found that 52% women are engaged in agriculture production with different activities harvesting, sowing, weeding and watering the crops. We found that 65% women are engaged in animal husbandry activities in the study area block Joya. Economic status of the agriculture labour especially women is very poor in rural areas, we found that 34.50% women's per month average income are below 2000 Rs. in agriculture sector. Gender discrimination in wages is present in rural areas in agriculture and animal husbandry activities.

Conclusion

Women are known as 'invisible farmers' in rural areas due to participation in agricultural activities. They are the backbone of rural agriculture development. They are performing crucial roles from sowing to marketing in agriculture. Women form a significant part of the agricultural workforce, often managing farms as men migrate for urban work. They are responsible for a vast majority of food production in India, handling labour intensive tasks like weeding, harvesting and processing. Their work extends to livestock rearing, poultry, fisheries and managing community ensuring, household nutrition and community resilience. Despite their massive contribution women have limited access to productive resources, owning significantly less land and facing barriers in wages in agriculture women bear the brunt of strenuous tasks like transplanting, weeding and carrying inputs, leading to high physical strain. Recognizing and supporting women's multifaceted roles in agriculture is not just a matter of gender equality but a necessity for India's agricultural advancement and national progress.

Women have the important place in progress the rural economy. They play multiple roles as farmers, wages earners, and entrepreneurs. They also care for the well being of their family members and are responsible for providing the food and care to the children and cattle. In the present study the researcher found that 77.50% women are engaged in primary sector, 16% are engaged in secondary sector and 6.50% women are engaged in territory sector in the study area. The participation of women has found 52% in agriculture and its activities and 65% women are engaged in animal husbandry activities. The economic status of women has found poor in the study area due to low income and unemployment. The gender discrimination in wages is present in the study area in agricultural labour, animal husbandry labour and unorganized sector of the study. So the participation of the women has an important place in primary sector and the important contribution in agriculture development in rural areas.

Suggestions for the future Study

Some suggestions are prepared by the researcher to develop the agriculture and animal husbandry. Which are as-

1. We need sustainable practices in agriculture and animal husbandry development. So modern farming is essential to increase the farmers income and improve the soil and production quality.
2. We should prefer dry agriculture and short term crops cultivation to improve the quality of soil and improve the underground water level. We should increase the area under the pulses and oil seeds crops to save the underground water.
3. Agro-based industries should be established in rural areas to control the poverty, unemployment and migration towards the urban areas.
4. We should develop the community fodder banks, improve pasture lands and promote sustainable grazies to develop the animal husbandry in rural areas.
5. We should develop the poultry farming, beekeeping, dairy farming and fisheries with the agriculture (crops) production to increase the farmers income and reduce the level of poverty in rural areas.
6. To save the environment we should management the crops waste and dung for organic compost development.

7. Finance facilities should be provided to the farmers in very low interest rate to develop the agriculture and dairy farming in rural areas.

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